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Unveiling the Champions Within: Exploring Mental Toughness Among University Athletes

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Abstract

Mental conditioning encompasses a wide range of mental skills such as focus, motivation, mental strength, and preparation for competition, aiming to enhance athletic performance and accelerate performance development. This qualitative research study on mental toughness among selected athletes employs a phenomenology to understand the lived experiences of individuals. Utilizing in-depth interviews as the primary data collection method, the study aims to capture profound insights into the athletes' perspectives, challenges faced, and psychological processes related to mental toughness. The study's respondents comprise five student-athletes who have encountered a common phenomenon of interest. Further, this study is anchored on the "Social Cognitive Theory" of Albert Bandura. In the context of mental toughness among athletes, Social Cognitive Theory could help in understanding how athletes observe and learn from others' behaviors and develop mental toughness through self-efficacy beliefs, goal setting, and self-regulation. The findings of the study shed light with the lived experiences of selected athletes regarding mental toughness, revealing two significant themes: embracing holistic growth and navigating challenges. These themes underscore the multifaceted nature of mental toughness and its profound influence on various aspects of athletes' lives, suggesting the need for comprehensive support systems and interventions to promote their holistic development and well-being.

Keywords: *mental conditioning, athletes, challenges, lived-experiences, sports*

Introduction

Mental conditioning involves training skills and attributes to enhance performance in various situations, such as focus, motivation, confidence, adaptability, mindfulness, relaxation, goal-setting, self-talk, imagery, breathing, and reflection according to Omaradzki (2022). However, mental conditioning in sports lies in the potential for athletes to face mental barriers that hinder their performance, such as low confidence, high anxiety, nerves, or feeling excessive pressure during competitions as stated by Duggan (2023).

Mental conditioning refers to the psychological techniques and processes utilized to enhance the mental toughness, focus, resilience, and overall performance of athletes according to Jeong et al. (2022). The problem addressed in his study revolves around understanding the complex interplay between coaching behavior, psychological needs, gender, and the mental conditioning process in Taekwondo Poomsae athletes. By investigating these relationships, the study aims to provide insights that can inform coaching practices and optimize athletes' psychological preparation and performance.

In the Philippines, particularly in the field of sports psychology or mental toughness among elite athletes, is gaining recognition and importance. Despite the growing interest in sports psychology research, De la Cerna and Diego (2022) state that there are challenges such as limited funding, infrastructure, and research capacity in some areas. However, these challenges also present opportunities for collaboration, innovation, and capacity-building efforts to further advance research in sports psychology in the Philippines.

In Surigao, Pagdato et al. (2021) states that mental toughness is likely defined as the psychological trait or capacity that enables athletes to maintain focus, determination, and resilience in the face of adversity or challenges encountered during training and competition. However, there may be cultural and contextual differences in how mental toughness is understood and valued among athletes, coaches, and sports practitioners. Furthermore, the relationship between motivation, mental toughness, and sports performance may not always be straightforward, as individual differences and external factors can influence athletes' responses to adversity and challenges.

Despite the growing interest in mental conditioning and mental toughness among elite athletes in the Philippines, there remains a research gap concerning the influence of cultural and contextual factors on the effectiveness of psychological interventions and the development of mental toughness. While existing studies emphasize the importance of mental conditioning techniques and the challenges faced by athletes, coaches, and sports practitioners, there is limited exploration of how cultural norms, societal expectations, and regional differences shape athletes' psychological preparation and response to adversity. Further research is needed to investigate these nuances, as understanding the cultural underpinnings of mental toughness can inform the design of tailored interventions and optimize athletes' psychological preparation and performance outcomes in the Philippine sporting context.

Research Objectives

The purpose of this study is to explore the lived experiences of selected athletes on mental toughness.

Methodology

This qualitative research study will utilize a descriptive comparative approach. According to Moroi T. (2021), qualitative research seeks to gain insights of phenomena through the collection of extensive data on many variables over an extended period of time, in a

naturalistic setting. This Phenomenological research is to capture the significance phenomenon, through reconnecting lived experiences of individuals according to Urcia (2021). In the context of this study, the researcher wanted to know the lived experiences of selected athletes regarding mental toughness.

In addition, the study will be conducted at an educational institution renowned for its excellence in providing higher education services situated along Bo. Obrero Street in Davao City. The study's respondents comprise five student-athletes who have encountered a common phenomenon of interest. The gathered data will be analyzed using thematic analysis. According to Clarke V. and Braun V. (2017) Thematic Analysis (TA) is a method for identifying, analyzing, and interpreting patterns of meaning ('themes') within qualitative data.

In gathering data for this study on mental toughness among selected athletes, it will conduct in-depth interviews to gain profound insights into their experiences, perspectives, and psychological processes. These interviews will serve as a crucial avenue for understanding the intricacies of mental toughness as perceived and embodied by the athletes themselves. By employing a semi-structured format, this will encourage participants to reflect on their journey, challenges faced, strategies employed, and moments of triumph. Through open-ended questions, this study aim to delve deep into the psychological dimensions of their performance, exploring aspects such as resilience, determination, focus, and emotional regulation. These in-depth interviews will not only provide valuable qualitative data but also afford participants a platform to articulate their experiences and insights, empowering them as active contributors to the research process.

Results and Discussion

This section summarizes key findings and highlights themes from interviews and group discussions, offering a narrative to give meaning to participants' experiences.

Lived Experiences of Selected Athletes on Mental Toughness

From the data gathered, there were two significant themes on the lived experiences of selected athletes I extracted from in-depth interview. These are the embracing holistic growth and navigating challenges.

Figure 1. *Emerging Themes on athletes lived experiences on mental toughness*

During interviews, students revealed a recurring struggle with embracing holistic growth and navigating challenges. Under the roof of holistic growth, three sub-themes emerged: adapting development, maintaining positive outlook and cultivating support from family and coach. On the latter part, three sub-themes emerged as well under significant theme navigating challenges: wrestling with pressures, managing discipline, and mastering time management.

Embracing Holistic Growth

Witnessing the experiences of these students, embracing holistic growth embarks on their journey in personal and professional development, athletes actively embrace the principle of holistic growth. The journey was enlightening and emotionally impactful. McLeod (2019) states that holistic growth emphasizes the development of an individual in all dimensions, encompassing physical, emotional, social, intellectual, and even spiritual well-being. This approach to personal development acknowledges the interconnectedness of these facets, emphasizing that nurturing each aspect contributes to a more balanced and fulfilled life. They navigate this dynamic path by continually cultivating support and mentorship, recognizing the integral role these relationships play in shaping their multifaceted advancement. In the present moment, they engage in practices that nurture not only their individual skills but also the interconnected aspects of their lives.

Adapting development. In my perspective as the interviewer, I sensed that adapting to self-development stands as a cornerstone to the success of students in engaging in sports. Participants described a range of observations that related to them student-athletes facilitating ongoing progression and development of skills, and adaptability to sustain growth. To wit, some of the participants had expressed:

"I find it entertaining specially playing ball games like basketball and volleyball until such time it became my hobby" - P2, IDI, L28-L29

"The reasons why I joined in sports is to make new friends and ahm to improve my skills" - P4, IDI, L82-L83

In the interviews, it has become apparent that the initial behaviors relate primarily to the processing of experiences through engagement with others, which provided the foundations for change in on-field actions. This result supports Anthony et. Al (2019) that when discussing the importance of being able to process information for development effectively, you yourself should have identified how an athlete considered mentally tough would work through a learning situation. First identify your skills, then discuss the learning points, and subsequently implement those learning points as a part of their future behavior.

Cultivating Support from Family. From an observer's standpoint, family plays a crucial role in the athlete's holistic growth. Family's unconditional love, encouragement and even emotional support is foundational to them during triumphs and even on setbacks where the athletes could feel that they are valued and supported.

"My source of inspiration are my family, friends and my partner." - P2, IDI, L30

The statement supports Parietti (2015), that the family influenced their faith and also motivation in achieving their goals in the sports. Apart from that, with the adequate family involvement in the athlete's sports, it created a harmonious environment and the athletes felt secure especially during the time they have to make an important decision in the sports career. In addition, the athletes perceived the close relationship with the parents was very important to them as the family could be the good listener, give emotional support and effective advice to them.

Cultivating Support from Coach. Notably from a researcher's standpoint, coach plays a significant role on the student's perspective. They serve as the athlete's guidance and inspiration to improve their skills and reach their full potentials. This is evident in the statements given by the participants that:

"My source of inspiration is ahm my PE teacher, "sir coach", I really like the way he teaches us and coaches us specific ways on how to learn the sport." - P4, IDI, L59-L60

The statement support the study of Jowett (2017) that coach serves as a mentor, instructor, motivator, and facilitator of growth for the athlete. Coaches provide technical guidance, strategic planning and skill development to help athletes improve their performance. Additionally, coaches offer emotional support, encouragement, and feedback to enhance athletes' confidence and motivation. They create a supportive and nurturing environment where athletes feel valued, respected, and empowered to reach their full potential. Moreover, coaches play a crucial role in fostering positive relationships and team dynamics, promoting collaboration, communication, and camaraderie among athletes. Overall, the coach is a central figure in the athlete's journey, influencing their motivation, development, and success both on and off the field.

Positive outlook. From the athletes, as a researcher I gathered the importance of having significant level of optimism and enthusiasm on their specific events in sport. The abundance of the athlete's positive emotions, thoughts and attitudes are high as they hope for the best. Specifically, it dwells with the statements given by the participant:

"Just don't mind the criticisms while playing even if you are not good at it." - P2, IDI, L36

These experience is also explained by Juan and Lopez (2015), when an athlete's attention and focus rate decreases, so does his or her self-confidence, according to a research on mental toughness in athletes (Omarfauzee et al., 2013). As a result, athletes must be able to harness energies that are negative (rehearsing a skill and routine or performance in mind, which are thought to help people relax. This positive view will assist athletes in controlling their anxiety. An athlete will never perform at his best no matter how great his skills are if he is not able to manage his apprehensions, fears, worries, anger and frustration before every event (Athans and Sampson, 2013). Thus, benefits from having control over unproductive negative energy results in positive competition outcomes.

Navigating Challenges

Athletes right now are dealing with stress and pressure to perform well. They're handling it by practicing a lot, building resilience to face and overcome these tough situations. This process includes teaching and inspiring others while also pushing through personal challenges, forming a tough mindset that helps in dealing with the ups and downs of life and work. To handle their time better, people are using simple strategies, adjusting to unexpected problems with alertness, and making smart changes. This overall idea highlights the active and ongoing approach needed to face challenges effectively, showing how dealing with stress, building resilience, pushing through personal struggles, and managing time are all interconnected in a dynamic way.

Pressure. Through interviews I've learned that dealing with pressure can be tough but it offers valuable lessons in resilience, problem-solving, and self-awareness. By handling pressure effectively, you uncover your strengths, weaknesses, and methods for excelling in difficult situations. These personal revelations can lead to growth, both in your professional and personal life, as you learn to navigate and conquer challenges with increased confidence and resilience. This is notable in the statement given by the participant that:

"there are a lot of pressure that I have experience so far especially when you are in a very competitive team so you really have to do good perform good in order for you to get praised and also ahmm acknowledged by everyone" - P4, IDI, L90-L94

This statement supports Allen et al. (2013) to where they defined mental toughness as a psychological quality that helps in coping with sport pressures and allows athletes to be consistently resolute in demonstrating psychological skills such as focus, motivation, confidence, and control as cited by Newland et al. (2013). In general, mental toughness seems to be most evident in situations where adversity is present. Pressure-filled game situations may warrant more mental toughness from athletes than games that are considered routine and not as meaningful (Ibid). According to Goldberg (2013), the ability to remain calm and composed under pressure, as well as the ability to concentrate on what's necessary and let go of everything else, are by far the two most crucial mental skills that make up the mental toughness umbrella. You will be totally lost as an athlete if you do not have these two vital mental skills. Championship athletes excel at concentration and the ability to stay focused in the face of adversity.

Time Management. As I have observed during the interview, it seems that planning, organizing and allocating time to academic task and sports activity seems hard but plays a vital role as a student-athlete. Athletes' prioritizing task, setting deadlines, and maximizing time helps them overcome all the required task both academically and in sports. This was clearly mentioned by the participants that:

"Time management is very important. You need to balance your studies and your non-academic activities. You need to prioritized your task and do not over commit yourself on a on an activities that aren't important" - P2, IDI, L42-L46

"Most of the time I really had a hard time in managing my time with my studies. It's because ahm I think ahm I'm a bit overwhelmed with school activities, and with trainings but I tried to manage it by doing the task that is ah lighter and then move after to as in more difficult task" - P4, IDI, L104-L107

Further the statements supports Macquet and Skalej (2015), elite athletes are expected to seek education in addition to sports training in order to prepare for life after their experience in sport (such as, Cosh and Tully, 2014). It is believed that time management has a significant impact on athletes' overall psychological state, mental recovery and physical aspect, inspiration, and perseverance in the face of hardship, injury rehabilitation, and results of the game (such as, Johnson and Podlog, 2014). Even though time management is a key factor, there has been little research into athletes' time. Effective time management enables athletes to balance their workload and meeting deadlines to achieve a better outcome.

Discipline. Filipino athletes learn discipline mainly through sports. This means they understand the importance of managing time well and following a routine, which helps them in their sports activities. Interestingly, they don't seem to focus on these things as much outside of sports. As I have observed, discipline for them is like a strict schedule that guides their lives, making sure they listen to their parents, teachers, and coaches, and stay focused on their tasks. This was clearly stated that:

"I usually set strict daily schedules for my sport and academic works. Ahmm I sort them base on their importance and urgency. That way I will not be bombarded with many different task on the same day." - P3, IDI, L74-L76

"So dapat alert ka and ready ka anytime. Kase hindi naman din sa lahat ng oras ahmm fix yung mangyayari. May mga changes talaga na mga instances na biglang susulpot tas maggugulo sa sched mo dapat alam mo din yun paano mag adjust pag nag gagawing solusyon and paano yung magiging ahm atake mo dun sa gagawin mo" - P5, IDI, L165-L169

Furthermore, this statement supports Garcia and Subia's (2019) study on high school athletes, self-discipline which refers to the ability of student-athletes to control their own behavior, emotions, and actions in pursuit of academic and athletic goals. It involves the capacity to stay focused, motivated, and organized despite challenges or distractions, as well as the willingness to make sacrifices and adhere to a structured routine. Self-discipline encompasses habits such as effective time management, goal-setting, perseverance, and self-regulation, all of which contribute to academic success and athletic performance. The study likely explores how self-discipline influences various aspects of student-athletes' lives, including their motivation, study habits, and overall academic performance.

Conclusions

The findings from the in-depth interviews with selected athletes shed light on the lived experiences of these individuals regarding mental toughness. Two significant themes emerged: embracing holistic growth and navigating challenges. Under the theme of embracing holistic growth, athletes discussed adapting development, maintaining a positive outlook, and cultivating support from family and coaches. On the other hand, navigating challenges encompassed wrestling with pressures, managing discipline, and mastering time management. These themes highlight the multifaceted nature of mental toughness and its influence on various aspects of athletes' lives, including personal development, relationships, and performance.

To contribute to the holistic development and well-being of athletes, universities must prioritize several key initiatives. Firstly, enhancing support systems is essential, involving coach training programs emphasizing mentorship and athlete development, along with initiatives to engage families in athletes' sporting journeys. Additionally, promoting positive mental strategies through mental skills training programs is crucial for athletes to manage pressure effectively and build resilience. Lastly, recognizing the importance of time management and discipline, universities should provide support mechanisms such as access to resources, academic support, and mentorship programs to help athletes balance their academic, athletic, and personal commitments. By addressing these commendations, universities can empower athletes to thrive both on and off the field, fostering their holistic growth and well-being.

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